

RESULTS OF A COMPARATIVE TESTING OF THE NEWLY DEVELOPED POTATO VARIETY “TASHKENT ERTAGISI” PLANTED IN THE VARIETY TESTING NURSERY IN AN EARLY PERIOD

Nizomov Rustam Akhrolovich

Rakhmatullayev Jasurbek Negmatullayevich

Scientific research institute of vegetable crops, melons and potatoes

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15142407>

Abstract: This article presents the results of comparative testing of the newly developed potato variety “Tashkent Ertagisi” against the standard “Sante” variety in the variety testing nursery during the early planting period.

According to the research results, the newly developed potato variety “Tashkent Ertagisi” manifested a 2-5 day earlier germination and flowering compared to the standard “Sante” variety, while in the number of stem and height of stem 10,9-15,6 % increase was noted, as well as a 18,2 % higher yield was observed.

Key words: variety testing nursery, variety, “Tashkent Ertagisi”, “Sante”, coefficient of variation, correlation coefficient, budding, flowering, stem height, number of stems, leaf surface, yield, profitability, economic efficiency.

Introduction. Potatoes are cultivated from the Arctic region to Transcaucasia, primarily in the Baltic republics, the Central Black Earth zone, the Volga region, Bashkortostan, the Urals, Siberia, and the Far East, as well as in the Central Asian republics. Potatoes have been cultivated in Uzbekistan for 150 years. In the world's leading potato-producing countries, one of the most pressing issues is the development of new adaptable and promising varieties, along with accelerated seed multiplication methods, to increase production volume and crop yield. In the potato industry of our republic, extensive efforts are being carried out to develop new competitive varieties for the global market, as well as to accelerate their multiplication and establish seed production systems. Potatoes are primarily propagated through tubers, making them the crop with the highest seed consumption per unit area (3.0–4.0 t/ha) [5;6;7;8;9;10].

RESEARCH CONDITIONS AND METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted in the experimental fields of the Tashkent Scientific-Experimental Station of the Research Institute of Vegetables, Melons, and Potato Crops during the years 2020-2021.

Field and production experiments, including planting, crop care, harvesting, calculation, and analysis, were carried out following generally accepted methodologies and the recommendations of the Ministry of Agriculture and

Water Resources, the All-Russian Institute of Plant Industry, the All-Russian Research Institute of Potato Farming, the Research Institute of Vegetables, Melons, and Potato Crops, and the State Commission for Testing New Varieties of Agricultural Crops of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1;2;3;4].

The statistical analysis of the results obtained from field experiments was performed using the B.A. Dospekhov method with the help of Microsoft Excel software.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the variety testing nursery, new potato varieties are studied for adaptation to ecological conditions, preservation of genetic traits, and their potential for efficient and stable adaptation in the future.

The phenological observation results of the “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” potato varieties planted in the variety testing nursery during the early planting period are presented in Table 1.

Table-1

The phenological observation results of the “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” potato varieties planted in the variety testing nursery during the early planting period (in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	Germination, day		From full germination to....., day			
			budding		flowering	
	10%	75%	10%	75%	10%	75%
Santé (st)	13	25	33	36	39	49
Tashkent Ertagisi	11	18	25	27	28	36
V%	12	25	25	30	28	33
V%	11	26	27	33	26	32

In accordance with the research results, in the standard "Sante" variety, germination of seedling was noted to be 10% in 13 days, 75% in 25 days, budding 10% in 33 days, 75% in 36 days, flowering 10% in 39 days, 75% in 47 days, while in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety the indicator was 10-75% for germination in 2-7 days, budding in 8-9 days and flowering in 11-13 days earlier than the standard variety.

The results of research also showed that in the “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” varieties planted in an early planting period, the coefficient of variation for 10% seedling germination ranged between 11-12%, indicating strong fluctuations. When 75% of the seedlings had emerged, the variation coefficient ranged between 25-26%, also showing strong fluctuations. From full

germination until 10-75% budding and flowering, the coefficient of variation remained high, ranging between 25-33%.

The biometric measurement results of the potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” which were planted in the variety testing nursery in an early planting period, are presented in Table 2.

Table-2

The biometric measurement results of the potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” planted in the variety testing nursery in an early planting period (in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	At the full flowering stage				Plant height at the harvesting period		Infection of plant by diseases, %	
	Stem height		Stem height		cm	relative to st,%	Fusarium	Anthracnose
	cm	relative to st,%	piece	relative to st,%				
Santé (st)	51,4	100,0	3,2	100,0	59,6	100,0	8	9
Tashkent Ertagisi	57,0	110,9	3,7	115,6	67,6	113,4	4	5
r=	0,83±0,17							
r=	0,80±0,20							

In the standard variety “Sante”, the stem height at the full flowering stage reached 51.4 cm (100%). In comparison, the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety had a stem height of 57 cm, which was 10.9% higher than the standard variety. Similarly, the number of stems was 15.6% higher, and at the full harvest stage, the stem height was 13.4% greater than that of the standard variety. Additionally, in these varieties, the infection rate of Fusarium and Anthracnose diseases ranged between 4–9%.

In the varieties planted in an early planting period, the correlation between stem height and the number of stems at full flowering was $r = 0.83 \pm 0.17$ in the standard “Sante” variety and $r = 0.80 \pm 0.20$ in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety. In both variants, the correlation was strong.

The weight of stems per plant, number of leaves, and leaf surface area of potato varieties planted in an early period in the variety testing nursery are presented in Table 3.

Table-3

The weight of stems per plant, number of leaves, and leaf surface of potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” planted in an early period in the variety testing nursery

(in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	Per plant						Leaf surface of the plant per ha, thousand m ²
	Stem weight		Number of leaves		Leaf surface		
	g	Relative to st, %	piece	Relative to st, %	dm ²	Relative to st, %	
“Sante”(st)	352,0	100,0	377,0	100,0	50,6	100,0	28,8
“Tashkent Ertagisi”	396,0	112,5	433,0	114,8	58,1	114,8	33,1

In “Sante” standard variety, the stem weight was 352.0 g and compared to this, in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety, the stem weight was 12.5% higher, the number of leaves increased by 14.8 %, and the leaf surface area was also 14.8 % higher.

The yield results of the newly developed potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” planted in the variety testing nursery in an early planting period are presented in Table 4.

Table-4

The yield results of the newly developed potato varieties “Sante” and “Tashkent Ertagisi” planted in the variety testing nursery in an early planting period (in 2020-2021)

Varietal samples	Harvesting time, day			Yield per plant, g	Yield, t/ha	Relative to standard, %
	60	70	80			
	Mean weight of tuber per plant, g					
“Sante” (st)	137,0	142,0	144,0	423,0	24,2	100,0
“Tashkent Ertagisi”	164,0	166,0	170,0	500,0	28,6	118,2
LSD ₀₅					1,9	
S_x , %					2,4	

In the variety testing nursery, the newly developed “Tashkent Ertagisi” potato variety was compared with the standard “Sante” variety in terms of harvest timing during early planting. The results of dynamic harvesting at 60, 70, and 80 days showed that the tuber weight per plant in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety increased by 77 grams more compared to the standard variety.

The yield of the standard “Sante” variety was 24.2 tons per hectare. In

comparison, the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety had a yield of 28.6 tons per hectare, which was 18.2% higher than the standard variety. The least significant difference (LSD_{05}) among all variants was determined to be 1.9 t/ha, and the experimental accuracy ($S_x, \%$) was 2.4%.

Economic efficiency

In a market economy, any new variety or technology must be economically beneficial; otherwise, it will not be adopted in production. Potato varieties recommended for farms and dehqan (smallholder) farms should be early-maturing, high-yielding, marketable, large-sized, and resistant to environmental conditions, diseases, and pests.

Table-5

The economic efficiency indicators of the “Tashkent Ertagisi” and “Sante” potato varieties planted in the variety testing nursery during the early planting period, ha/thousand UZS (in 2020-2021)

Indicators	Varietal samples	
	Tashkent Ertagisi	Sante (st)
Seed, fertilizer, fuel & lubricants, cultivation and other expenses	18280,0	18280,0
Harvesting and transportation costs	2860,0	2420,0
Total expenses	21140,0	20700,0
Overhead costs , 25%	5285,0	5175,0
Unforeseen expenses (20%)	5285,0	5175,0
All expenses	31710,0	31050,0
Yield, t/ha	28,6	24,2
Crop price, UZS 2300	65780,0	55660,0
Net profit	34070,0	24610,0
Cost price per 1 ton of product	1071,8	1240,3
Profitability level, %	107,4	79,2

When calculating the yield of the tested varieties, we used the "Technological Map for Potato Cultivation". All incurred expenses were carried out according to the following directions.

In the technological map for potato cultivation, overhead costs are set at 25%. Accordingly, these costs were calculated based on the total expenses, with an additional deduction of 20% for unforeseen expenses. The total expenses consisted of overhead costs (25%) and unforeseen expenses (20%), which were added together to form the overall expenditure. The costs for harvesting and transportation were dependent on the yield per hectare.

In the standard “Sante” variety, the profitability level was 79.2%, while in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety, this indicator increased to 107.4%.

Conclusion

1. According to the research results, in the standard “Sante” variety, potato germination was observed as follows: 10% emergence in 13 days, 75% emergence in 25 days; 10% budding in 33 days, 75% budding in 36 days; 10% flowering in 39 days, 75% flowering in 47 days. In contrast, in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety, the 10-75% germination, budding, and flowering occurred earlier than the standard variety by: 2-7 days for germination, 8-9 days for budding, 11-13 days for flowering.

2. In the early planting period, the stem height of the standard “Sante” variety at the full flowering stage reached 51.4 cm (100%). In comparison, the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety had a stem height of 57 cm, which was 10.9% higher than the standard variety. Similarly, the number of stems was 15.6% higher than in the standard variety, and at the full harvest stage, the stem height exceeded the standard variety by 13.4%. Additionally, the incidence of Fusarium and Anthracnose diseases in these varieties ranged between 4-9%.

3. In the early planting varieties, at the full flowering stage, the correlation between stem height and the number of stems was $r = 0.83 \pm 0.17$ in the standard “Sante” variety while in “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety $r = 0.80 \pm 0.20$. In both varieties, the correlation was strong.

4. In the standard “Sante” variety, the stem weight was 352.0 g. Compared to this, in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety stem weight was 12.5% higher, number of leaves was 14.8% higher, leaf surface area was 14.8% higher. Additionally, the profitability level in the “Sante” variety was 79.2%, whereas in the “Tashkent Ertagisi” variety, it increased to 107.4%.

References:

1. Dospekhov B.A. Methodology of Field Experiments with Fundamentals of Statistical Data Processing. – Moscow: Alliance, 2011. – p.351.
2. Litvinov S.S. Methodology of Field Experiments in Vegetable Growing. – Moscow: GNU VNIIO, 2011. – p.648.
3. Methodology for State Variety Testing of Agricultural Crops. Issue 1. General Part. – Moscow, 2019. – p.329.
4. R.A. Nizomov et al. Methods for Conducting Experiments on Vegetable, Melon, and Potato Crops. – Tashkent, 2023. – Pp. 204-217.34
5. Ostonakulov T.E et al. Vegetable Growing. – Tashkent, 2018. – p. 285.
6. Ostonakulov T.E. Potato Growing. – Tashkent. Agrobank, 2021. – p.96.

7. Ostonakulov T.E., Makhamatova M.M. General Selection and Seed Production. Study Guide. – Tashkent, 2024. – p.304.
8. Kholdorov M.U., Ismoilov A.I., Ostonakulov T.E., Oblokulov F.A. The impact of planting dates and depth on early potato growth, leaf surface formation, and yield // Bulletin of the Khorezm Mamun Academy. Khorezm, 2023. Issue 11, - pp. 174-176.
9. Ergashev I.T., Eshonqulov B.M., Normurodov D.S., Oblokulov F.A. Potato breeding and seed production. Samarkand, 2021. - pp. 39-40.
10. Khamzaev A.Kh. Early and high-quality potato cultivation – an urgent issue // Journal Agro Ilm. 2018. Issue 2, - pp. 50-51.